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IMPORTANCE OF MICROCLIMATE INDICATORS IN THE COWSHED

Kholbekova M.B.¹

PhD student,

¹Samarkand State University of Veterinary Medicine,
Animal Husbandry and Biotechnology, Uzbekistan.

Amirov Sh.K.²

²Supervisor, T.S.A.U, Samarkand branch.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7229225>

Annotation: In the article, the system and methods of keeping cows at the "Khamid Livestock Oasis" farm, as well as the data obtained from the study of the microclimate indicators in the cowshed in the cross-section of the seasons of the year, are highlighted. It was observed that the microclimate indicators were at the level required by zoo hygienic standards in the winter, spring and autumn seasons. Due to the hot summer season, the temperature, relative humidity, and amount of ammonia gas in the cowshed were somewhat expected. Air movement speed, on the other hand, was lower than normal.

Key words: Cow, Estonian red breed, livestock, zoo hygienic requirements, microclimate indicators, temperature, relative humidity, air movement speed, etc.

Introduction. Cattle industry plays an important role in meeting the growing population's need for milk and meat. Increasing the milk productivity of cows is one of the important factors in solving this problem.

In the breeding of livestock products, improving the genetic quality of livestock remains relevant. In this case, it is necessary to improve the work of breeding in networks, using all modern achievements of biological science. In particular, the use of interior indicators of animals in the process, appropriate use, arouses great interest among practitioners.

Animal interior performance depends on several factors. Among them, the following can be considered the main ones: productivity, physiological state, level and type of feeding, season of the year, storage conditions, breed, etc.

External conditions, such as air temperature, relative humidity, air movement speed, and the amount of gases in the barn, have a direct effect on blood and through it on productivity.

By determining the amount of these indicators, it is possible to evaluate the zoo hygienic condition of the cowshed. Deviation of the farm weather indicators from the normative requirements in a negative direction has a negative effect on the organism of cows and this is reflected in the productivity. On the other hand, the cows cannot reveal their productivity in their genetic potential [1; 2; 3; 4].

Taking into account the above-mentioned points, in our research, we tried to study the method of keeping cows on the farm, the microclimate indicators in the cow shed during the seasons of the year.

The purpose of the study: to determine the microclimate indicators in the cowshed in order to study the suitability of the method of keeping cows in the farm to zoo hygienic requirements.

Research object and applied methods: The research was conducted at the farm "Hamid Livestock Oasis" in Pasterdargom District. As a result of the research, the method of keeping cows and the microclimate indicators in the cowshed were evaluated.

For the experiment, two groups of Estonian red cows were formed according to breed, age at birth, live weight, and milk yield. Milk and meat to group I; 15 cows (30 cows in total) were included in the II group. A mixed method recommended by the scientists of our country was used to keep cows. Mature cows of different production types, cowshed weather indicators were used as research subjects.

Zoo technical and zoo hygienic methods were used in performing the tasks defined in the research.

Research results. It is known that the milk yield of cows depends to some extent on the system and methods of keeping them. In foreign and advanced experiences, 4 systems of cow keeping are used: barn, barn-pasture, pasture and barn-camp. In keeping cows, methods of keeping with and without tying are used. However, when using the system and methods of keeping cows, it is necessary to take into account the natural climate and economic conditions of the existing farm.

Due to the climatic and economic conditions of the farm where the experiments were conducted, a mixed method was used for keeping cows. Cows were fed in different seasons of the year on cold (winter) and rainy (spring) days in the "Hamid Livestock Oasis" farm, and in the pastures on warm days. We had to keep the cows in the barn during the heat of the summer and let them out to the pasture as soon as it cooled down.

In order to evaluate the zoohygienic condition of the cowshed, we determined microclimate indicators (temperature, relative humidity, air movement speed), gas content (ammonia gas concentration). The obtained data were summarized and presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Change of microclimatic parameters in the cowshed during the seasons

indicators	Measure unit	The norm	Real condition
Autumn			
Temperature	°C	10	22
Relative humidity	%	70	72
Amount of ammonia gas	mg/m ³	20	20
Air movement speed	m/s	0,5	0,4
Winter			
Temperature	°C	10	12
Relative humidity	%	70	70
Amount of ammonia gas	mg/m ³	20	20,5
Air movement speed	m/s	0,5	0,4
Spring			
Temperature	°C	10	23
Relative humidity	%	70	73
Amount of ammonia gas	mg/m ³	20	19,5
Air movement speed	m/s	0,5	0,3
Summer			
Temperature	°C	10	30
Relative humidity	%	70	78
Amount of ammonia gas	mg/m ³	20	22,2
Air movement speed	m/s	0,5	0,2

As can be seen from the table, the temperature in the cowshed was +13 0C above the norm in autumn, and the relative humidity was +2% above the norm, being 72% in these seasons. Relative humidity was 3% higher, ammonia content and air movement speed can be assessed as normal. Microclimatic indicators in the cowshed in autumn: temperature, relative humidity, ammonia content, air movement speed, respectively 12 0C; 72%; it was found to be 20 ml/m³ and 0.4 m/c. It was also found that the temperature index was high, i.e. +13 0C higher than the norm. It should be noted that the body of cows begins to have a negative effect when the temperature exceeds +25 degrees. In this case, breathing and heart rate increase. Due to this, changes are observed in the composition of the blood, even if it is small.

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In Uzbekistan, the summer season is very hot, and it is difficult to keep cows in this season. The hot time of the day lasts from 11:00 to 17:00. Therefore, this time duration is equal to 6 hours or 25% of the day. At this time, experimental cows were kept in a barn, large doors were opened, and local materials were used in the construction of the barn, which allowed the cowshed to be somewhat cool. Nevertheless, it was observed that the temperature in the cowshed increased by 20 0C, the relative humidity by 8%, and the amount of ammonia gas by 2.2 ml/m³. The speed of air movement was 0.2 m/c, showing a slower indicator. This situation caused some changes in the cows' body.

Summary. From the indicators of the microclimate in the farm, it can be concluded that the worst indicators were determined in the summer season. It had a slight, though not serious, effect on the blood composition and clinical parameters of the cows. We will provide relevant information in our future articles. Microclimatic indicators in the cowshed did not change sharply from the requirements of the zoo hygienic standard in seasons other than the warm summer season. Alternatively, some changes in it did not have a negative effect on the body of cows.

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